

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NEOKEYNESIANISM AND NEOPROTECTIONISM IN THE CONTEXT OF MITIGATING ECONOMIC INEQUALITY AND PRESERVING GLOBAL SECURITY

Sokhatskyi O.

PhD International Economic Relations

Doctoral student

West Ukrainian National University

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/000-0001-8735-866X>

ABSTRACT

The article examines the concepts of Neokeynesianism and Neoprotectionism in the context of the modern economy, which faces challenges such as globalization, income inequality, and instability. It explores tools of government intervention, including investments in infrastructure, stimulation of domestic demand, and support for social programs, as the foundation of the Keynesian approach. The role of protectionist measures, such as non-tariff barriers, subsidies for strategic sectors, and import restrictions, is also analyzed in ensuring economic stability and safeguarding national interests. Examples of successful implementation of these strategies in the European Union, the United States, and Japan are provided, demonstrating their potential to reduce inequality, stimulate GDP growth, and create jobs. It is determined that the synergy of Neokeynesian and protectionist approaches contributes to sustainable economic development, reduces social tensions, and enhances global security.

Keywords: Neokeynesianism, Neoprotectionism, economic inequality, government regulation, globalization, global security.

Problem Statement

The processes of globalization have opened unprecedented opportunities for the development of international cooperation, technological progress, and economic growth. At the same time, they have led to significant challenges, notably the intensification of economic inequality. In the current context of global integration, national economies face a series of problems, including dependency on global markets, uneven resource distribution, and widening economic disparities between countries with varying levels of development. Domestically, income inequality and limited access to basic social services become sources of social tension, complicating economic and social progress.

Under these conditions, the theories of Neokeynesianism and Neoprotectionism provide a foundation for developing new approaches to addressing inequality and achieving economic stability. Neokeynesianism emphasizes the importance of active state intervention in economic processes, particularly through investments in infrastructure, employment stimulation, and support for consumer demand. This approach helps reduce socio-economic imbalances and creates conditions for sustainable development. On the other hand, Neoprotectionism focuses on protecting national economies from the adverse effects of globalization by introducing non-tariff barriers, subsidizing local producers, and restricting the import of strategically significant goods.

Historical experience confirms the effectiveness of these approaches. In the 1930s, the Keynesian "New Deal" program in the United States became a key tool for overcoming the effects of the Great Depression. Large-scale investments in transportation and energy infrastructure, job creation, and support for the agricultural sector helped stabilize the economy and reduce social inequality. Similar programs are currently being

implemented in European Union countries, where efforts are focused on stimulating "green" technologies, investing in renewable energy, and developing innovative sectors.

Neoprotectionism, as a modern approach to addressing economic challenges, emphasizes maintaining the competitiveness of national economies. For instance, Japan utilizes state subsidies to support high-tech industries, such as robotics and electronics, enabling it to maintain a leading position in the global market. Similarly, China actively pursues policies to promote local production, enhancing the country's economic autonomy and reducing reliance on imports.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications

The topic of applying Neokeynesian and Neoprotectionist approaches has attracted the attention of numerous domestic and international scholars. For instance, Joseph Stiglitz, in his work *"Freefall: America, Free Markets, and the Sinking of the World Economy"* (2010), emphasizes the importance of government intervention in overcoming economic crises. He argues that investments in social projects and infrastructure are key to reducing inequality and ensuring sustainable development.

Ukrainian researchers have also explored these issues. For example, O.I. Amosha and S.V. Kuzmenko, in their article *"The Role of State Regulation in Economic Development"* (2020), analyze the impact of public investments on reducing social disparities. The authors highlight that support for the healthcare and education sectors contributes not only to economic but also to social growth, particularly in crisis-stricken countries.

Regarding Neoprotectionism, significant contributions have been made by Dani Rodrik and Mary Kal-dor. In his book *"The Globalization Paradox"* (2011), Rodrik focuses on the importance of preserving economic autonomy for states in a globalized world. He

underscores the effectiveness of non-tariff barriers, quality standards, and subsidies in protecting domestic producers in a competitive environment.

The study by I.I. Yeliseeva, "*Protectionism as a Tool of Economic Security*" (2021), highlights the advantages of state support for strategic sectors, including the agricultural complex and high-tech industries. The author emphasizes that such measures ensure economic resilience and minimize the negative impact of external factors on the national economy.

Contemporary research confirms the relevance of applying Neokeynesianism and Neoprotectionism to address pressing economic challenges. However, the issue of integrating these approaches into a unified political strategy remains unresolved and requires further academic exploration.

The aim of this article is to provide a theoretical substantiation and empirical verification of the effectiveness of Neokeynesianism and Neoprotectionism in mitigating inequality and increasing per capita income amid global instability and the Russia-Ukraine war. The article seeks to identify opportunities for integrating these approaches to achieve economic stability, reduce social tensions, and ensure sustainable development in a globalized context. The research results will contribute to the development of practical recommendations for formulating national economic strategies focused on reducing inequality and enhancing social justice.

Presentation of the Main Material

The processes of globalization in the 21st century have profoundly transformed the global economy, offering new opportunities for international cooperation while simultaneously posing serious challenges. One of the primary objectives of contemporary economic policy is to find ways to address economic inequality, driven by uneven access to resources and income. To examine this issue, it is instructive to analyze three major economies — the United States, Russia, and China — each demonstrating distinct approaches to tackling these challenges.

The U.S. economic model is rooted in Neokeynesian principles, emphasizing active government intervention in regulating economic processes. Key tools include investments in infrastructure projects, technological innovation, and employment support programs. In 2023, the GDP per capita in the U.S. reached \$70,248, reflecting the country's high level of economic development.

Russia, on the other hand, adheres to protectionist approaches, focusing state support on strategic sectors such as energy and the military-industrial complex. These measures ensure economic stability even during periods of crisis. In 2023, Russia's GDP per capita was \$12,194, and the unemployment rate stood at 4.6%.^[1]

China's economic strategy combines elements of protectionism with active promotion of exports and domestic demand. As a result, in 2023, its GDP per capita reached \$12,174, while unemployment remained at 5.0%, demonstrating the resilience of its economy in the face of global challenges. Income inequality remains one of the most pressing issues for all three countries. In the U.S., the Gini index stood at 41.5 in 2023,

indicating a significant level of social stratification. In Russia and China, the Gini index was lower, at 37.5 and 38.5, respectively, suggesting relatively more effective mechanisms for state income redistribution.

The dynamics of GDP per capita over the past five years indicate stable growth in all three countries, albeit at varying rates. In the U.S., gradual growth was observed, rising from \$65,297 in 2019 to \$70,248 in 2023, despite a temporary decline in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Russia faced more challenging growth conditions due to sanctions and its reliance on raw material exports. However, protectionist measures, including subsidies for strategic sectors, enabled GDP per capita to grow from \$11,500 in 2019 to \$12,194 in 2023.

China demonstrated more consistent development thanks to its significant export potential and state support for high-tech industries. From 2019 to 2023, GDP per capita increased from \$10,280 to \$12,174. Investments in domestic market development and support for small businesses also contributed to reducing unemployment.

Unemployment rates varied depending on macroeconomic conditions and crises. In the U.S., unemployment surged to 8.1% in 2020 due to the pandemic, but thanks to government support, it stabilized at 3.7% by 2023. In Russia and China, such fluctuations were less pronounced due to domestic labor market regulation.

The Gini index reflects the effectiveness of measures to reduce economic inequality. In China, it decreased from 39.1 in 2019 to 38.5 in 2023, while in Russia, it fell from 38.0 to 37.5. In the U.S., this index remained relatively stable, indicating limited effectiveness of social programs.

This comparative analysis highlights the potential of Neokeynesian and protectionist strategies to address economic inequality and achieve sustainable development in the face of global challenges.

One of the key factors influencing macroeconomic stability is the efficiency of government investments in strategic industries. In the United States, active investments in renewable energy, innovation, and transportation infrastructure have become a significant driver of economic growth. These investments create new jobs and strengthen domestic demand.

In Russia, protectionist measures, such as subsidies for the agricultural sector and energy industry, have helped maintain economic stability under the pressure of sanctions. State support for export-oriented sectors has allowed the country to sustain its economy.

China, through its large-scale government programs, stimulates innovation in high-tech industries such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and green energy. Investments in these sectors have contributed to GDP growth and job creation, positively impacting employment levels.^[2]

Economic stability also depends on the adaptability of government policies to crisis phenomena. The United States demonstrated the effectiveness of its Keynesian mechanisms during the COVID-19 pandemic, when the government actively stimulated demand through direct payments to the population and support for small businesses.

Russia, maintaining its focus on protectionism, concentrated on strengthening its domestic market by supporting key industries and protecting against import pressures. This approach minimized economic losses even during periods of global instability.

China is actively developing both its domestic market and export opportunities, with significant attention given to expanding trade ties with developing countries. As a result, the country maintains a stable level of economic growth despite global challenges.

Fig. 1. Comparison of Macroeconomic Indicators of the USA, Russia, and China in 2023 [1]

- The figure presents three key macroeconomic indicators: GDP per capita, unemployment rate, and Gini index for the USA, Russia, and China in 2023.

- The first graph shows a significantly higher GDP per capita in the USA (\$70,248) compared to Russia (\$12,194) and China (\$12,174).

- The second graph illustrates the unemployment rate: the lowest in the USA (3.7%), slightly higher in Russia (4.6%) and China (5.0%).

- The third graph represents the Gini index: the highest in the USA (41.5), slightly lower in China (38.5) and Russia (37.5), indicating the level of income inequality in these countries.

The effectiveness of combining Keynesian and protectionist approaches becomes evident when analyzing unemployment rates. In the United States, demand-stimulation measures enabled a swift return to pre-crisis employment levels. Meanwhile, Russia and China demonstrate stability through effective labor market regulation.

Social policy also plays a critical role in reducing income inequality. In China, poverty alleviation programs have significantly lowered the Gini index over the past decade, fostering social cohesion and overall economic efficiency.

Russia, focusing on resource redistribution, supports the most vulnerable groups through subsidies and social programs. This approach reduces social tensions and sustains domestic consumption. Despite high income levels, the United States faces persistent inequality, one of the highest among developed countries. The limited effectiveness of social programs highlights the need to improve mechanisms for income redistribution.

The data suggest that a synergy of Keynesian and protectionist approaches can be an effective tool for ensuring economic stability. For example, in China, state support for technology development is accompanied by stimulation of domestic demand, promoting sustainable growth.

In Russia, the domestic market serves as a key instrument of economic resilience. Protectionist measures preserve the competitiveness of local companies even under sanctions pressure. The United States actively invests in new technologies and innovations, ensuring long-term competitiveness. Support programs for "green energy" also drive job growth in relevant sectors.

An analysis of macroeconomic indicator dynamics shows that each of the three countries demonstrates its own development model. The United States leverages the advantages of domestic demand, Russia focuses on protecting strategic industries, and China enhances export opportunities.

In conclusion, integrating various economic approaches allows for achieving high long-term results. The examples of these three countries underscore the necessity of adapting strategies to specific conditions and challenges.

The effectiveness of combining Keynesian and protectionist approaches becomes evident when analyzing unemployment rates. In the United States, demand-stimulation measures enabled a swift return to pre-crisis employment levels. Meanwhile, Russia and China demonstrate stability through effective labor market regulation.

Social policy also plays a critical role in reducing income inequality. In China, poverty alleviation programs have significantly lowered the Gini index over the past decade, fostering social cohesion and overall economic efficiency.

Russia, focusing on resource redistribution, supports the most vulnerable groups through subsidies and social programs. This approach reduces social tensions and sustains domestic consumption. Despite high income levels, the United States faces persistent inequality, one of the highest among developed countries. The limited effectiveness of social programs highlights the need to improve mechanisms for income redistribution.

The data suggest that a synergy of Keynesian and protectionist approaches can be an effective tool for ensuring economic stability. For example, in China, state support for technology development is accompanied by stimulation of domestic demand, promoting sustainable growth.

In Russia, the domestic market serves as a key instrument of economic resilience. Protectionist measures preserve the competitiveness of local companies even under sanctions pressure. The United States actively invests in new technologies and innovations, ensuring long-term competitiveness. Support programs for "green energy" also drive job growth in relevant sectors.

An analysis of macroeconomic indicator dynamics shows that each of the three countries demonstrates its own development model. The United States leverages the advantages of domestic demand, Russia focuses on protecting strategic industries, and China enhances export opportunities.

In conclusion, integrating various economic approaches allows for achieving high long-term results. The examples of these three countries underscore the necessity of adapting strategies to specific conditions and challenges.

References

1. World Bank. (2023). GDP per Capita Data. URL: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>
2. International Labour Organization. (2023). Global Employment Trends. URL: <https://www.ilo.org/global/statistics-and-databases/lang--en/index.htm>
3. United Nations Development Programme. (2023). Human Development Reports: Gini Index. URL: <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/GII>
4. OECD. (2023). Economic Outlook: Income Inequality and Social Mobility. URL: <https://www.oecd.org/economy/outlook/>
5. IMF. (2023). World Economic Outlook: Growth Trends and Projections. URL: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO>
6. National Bureau of Statistics of China. (2023). Statistical Yearbook. URL: <http://www.stats.gov.cn/>
7. U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis. (2023). National Economic Accounts. URL: <https://www.bea.gov/>
8. The Economist Intelligence Unit. (2023). Global Economic Forecasts. URL: <https://www.eiu.com/>
9. UNCTAD. (2023). Trade and Development Report: Globalization Trends. URL: <https://unctad.org/>
10. Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*. Harvard University Press.
11. Piketty, T. (2014). *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*. Harvard University Press. URL: <https://www.hup.harvard.edu/catalog.php?isbn=9780674430006>
12. Krugman, P. (1994). *The Age of Diminished Expectations*. MIT Press. URL: <https://mitpress.mit.edu/9780262610957/the-age-of-diminished-expectations/>
13. Stiglitz, J. E. (2012). *The Price of Inequality: How Today's Divided Society Endangers Our Future*. W.W. Norton & Company. URL: <https://wwnorton.com/books/the-price-of-inequality>
14. Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*. Palgrave Macmillan. URL: <https://www.macmillanihe.com/page/detail/the-general-theory-of-employment-interest-and-money-john-maynard-keynes/?sf1=barcode&st1=9780230004764>
15. Rodrik, D. (2011). *The Globalization Paradox: Democracy and the Future of the World Economy*. W.W. Norton & Company. URL: <https://wwnorton.com/books/the-globalization-paradox>
16. Reinhart, C. M., & Rogoff, K. S. (2009). *This Time Is Different: Eight Centuries of Financial Folly*. Princeton University Press. URL: <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691152646/this-time-is-different>
17. Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. A. (2012). *Why Nations Fail: The Origins of Power, Prosperity, and Poverty*. Crown Business. URL: <https://whynationsfail.com/>
18. Milanovic, B. (2016). *Global Inequality: A New Approach for the Age of Globalization*. Harvard University Press. URL: <https://www.hup.harvard.edu/catalog.php?isbn=9780674737136>
19. Mazzucato, M. (2013). *The Entrepreneurial State: Debunking Public vs. Private Sector Myths*. Anthem Press. URL: <https://anthempress.com/the-entrepreneurial-state>
20. Baldwin, R. (2016). *The Great Convergence: Information Technology and the New Globalization*. Harvard University Press. URL: <https://www.hup.harvard.edu/catalog.php?isbn=9780674660489>